

Job Satisfaction Mediates the Influence of Reward and Work Discipline on Employee Performance: Study on Grab Partner Driver in Jakarta

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Abstract

In general, the aims of this research are 1) to know and analyze the effect of rewards on job satisfaction of Grab employees in Jakarta, 2) to know and analyze the influence of work discipline on job satisfaction of Grab employees in Jakarta, 3) to know and analyze the effect of rewards on the performance of Grab employees in Jakarta, 4) Knowing and analyzing the effect of work discipline on Grab employee performance in Jakarta, 5) Knowing and analyzing the effect of job satisfaction on Grab employee performance in Jakarta, 6) Knowing and analyzing the mediation of job satisfaction on the effect of rewards on Grab employee performance in Jakarta, 7) Knowing and analyzing the mediation of job satisfaction on the effect of work discipline on the performance of Grab employees in Jakarta. The unit of analysis is 100 Grab drivers in Jakarta. The research was conducted by using a questionnaire measured by a Likert scale. The research method is quantitative, and this research is a causal associative research. The data analysis technique in this study used path analysis, where data processing was carried out using the SmartPLS 3.0 program. The results showed 1) Rewards had a positive and significant effect on Grab employee job satisfaction in Jakarta, 2) Work discipline had a positive and significant effect on Grab employee job satisfaction in Jakarta, 3) Rewards did not affect Grab employee performance in Jakarta, 4) Work discipline has a positive and significant effect on the performance of Grab employees in Jakarta, 5) Job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on the performance of Grab employees in Jakarta, 6) Job satisfaction mediates the effect of reward on Grab

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1. Introduction

Various studies have been conducted on the factors affecting employee performance, including reward, work discipline, and job satisfaction. In several previous studies, there are still differences in research results (research gaps) regarding factors that influence employee performance. This study tries to find out what factors influence the performance of Grab employees. The variables used in this study were job satisfaction as a mediating variable and rewards and work discipline, which were tested for their effect on employee performance.

Performance (work achievement) records the results from certain job functions or activities during a certain period (Bernardin and Russel in Sutrisno, 2019). Performance is the result of work achieved by someone based on job requirements. A job has certain requirements to be carried out in achieving goals, which are also known as work standards (Bangun, 2016). Fahmi (2018) said performance is the result obtained by an organization; both the organization is profit-oriented and non-profit-oriented, which is produced over time. Based on these descriptions, it can be concluded that performance is a result of an employee's work in a process or carrying out tasks according to his responsibilities in a certain period, which can affect the achievement of a particular organization.

Job satisfaction is a level of positive and pleasing individual emotions. In other words, job satisfaction results from an individual's estimation of work or positive and pleasant experiences (Wijono, 2018). Job satisfaction is a feeling that supports or does not support employees related to their work or condition (Mangkunegara, 2017). Job satisfaction depends on what an employee wants from his job and what they get. The most dissatisfied employees are those who want the most and get the least. Meanwhile, those who feel most satisfied want a lot and get it (Moorse in Panggabean, 2016).

Reward uses all motivating situations, starting from the biological drive, a person's main need, to the results that provide rewards for someone, such as money, affection, and high-level social aspirations (Djaali, 2018). Rewards are a form of reward given to employees who can get certain achievements that are beneficial to the company or organization in financial and non-financial forms in order to increase enthusiasm, motivate employee commitment, and influence other employees to do even better so that competition occurs—positive relationship between employees (Busro, 2018).

Discipline is a feeling of obedience and obedience to the work that is the responsibility. This discipline is closely related to authority. If authority does not work properly, then discipline will disappear. Therefore, the authority holder must be able to instill self-discipline so that he has responsibility for work in accordance with the authority he has (Ansory and Indrasari, 2018). Hasibuan (2019) defines discipline as defined as written or unwritten behavior.

2. Materials and Methods

This study uses a non-probability sampling technique because the number of population members is unknown. Researchers used a non-probability sampling technique. Sugiyono (2018) said that a non-probability sampling technique is a sampling technique that only provides an opportunity for some elements or members of the population to be selected as a sample. This technique includes systematic sampling, quota, accidental, purposive, saturated, and snowball—research using a purposive sampling technique. Sugiyono (2018) defines purposive sampling as a technique with certain considerations.

Sources of data needed in this study are primary data, questionnaires to respondents, interviews with sources, and secondary data through literature in books, journals, laws and regulations, and seminar results. Population is an area of generalization of objects that have certain qualities and characteristics determined by researchers to be studied and then draw conclusions (Sugiyono, 2018). Determination of the population is an important stage in research. The population in this study are all Grab drivers in Jakarta. The research method is quantitative, and this research is a causal associative research.

3. Results and Discussions

Validity Test

Based on the PLS method, testing the validity of reflexive indicators is carried out in 2 stages. The first stage is testing convergent validity, namely testing validity based on the loading factor value of each construct, and the next stage is testing discriminant validity, namely testing validity based on comparisons.

a) Convergent Validity

Testing the validity of the first stage is used to identify that the unobserved variable can be measured using each observed variable construct through Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA), commonly referred to as factor analysis, by looking at the loading factor. The loading factor is a number that shows the correlation between the score of an item in question and the score of the construct indicators that measure the construct. The loading factor value greater than 0.70 is said to be valid. After processing the data using SmartPLS 3.0, the loading factor results are presented in Figure 1. as follows:

Source: Results of analysis using SmartPLS 3.0. (2023)

Figure 1.

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Path Loading Factor Stage I

Based on Figure 1. above, it is known that the loading factor values are summarized in Table 1. following:

Table 1.
Loading Factor Value

No.	Indicator	Rewards (X1)	Work Discipline (X2)	Job satisfaction (X3)	Employee performance (Y)
1.	Item_01	0.787	0.794	0.783	0.836
2.	Item_02	0.805	0.775	0.786	0.852
3.	Item_03	0.835	0.811	0.764	0.801
4.	Item_04	0.804	0.771	0.768	0.868
5.	Item_05	0.828	0.786	0.758	0.848
6.	Item_06	0.771	0.818	0.772	0.882
7.	Item_07	0.778	0.769	0.771	0.859
8.	Item_08	0.809	0.777	0.759	0.738
9.	Item_09	0.822	0.824	0.809	0.748
10.	Item_10	0.752	0.782	0.761	0.071

b) Discriminant Validity

The next validity test is discriminant validity testing. This test is based on the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) value. The AVE value is good if greater than 0.50 (Ghozali, 2017). The following are values from the AVE table:

Table 2.
AVE (Average et al.) Value

No.	Variable	AVE Value
1.	Rewards(X1)	0.636
2.	Work Discipline (X2)	0.629
3.	Job Satisfaction (X3)	0.600
4.	Employee Performance (Y)	0.675

Source: Results of analysis using SmartPLS 3.0. (2023)

Table 2. above shows the AVE value of the research model. It can be seen from the table that the AVE value for all research variables and research dimensions has a value above 0.50, so the AVE value for discriminant validity testing is sufficient for further testing. Thus, the Discriminant Validity test has been fulfilled, as well as the Convergent Validity test, so that it can be concluded that the research model is valid.

Readability Test

A reliability test is a reliability test that aims to determine how far a measuring instrument can be relied upon or trusted. It is found that each variable has a composite reliability value above 0.70, with the lowest value of 0.953 from the work discipline variable (X1) and the highest value of 0.955 from the job satisfaction variable (X3). From these results, the research model meets the value of composite reliability. While the Cronbach's alpha value from the table research model shows that each variable has a Cronbach's alpha value above 0.60 with the lowest value of 0.947 from the work discipline variable (X2) and employee performance (Y) and the highest value is 0.949 from the job satisfaction variable (X3). From these results, the research model meets the value of Cronbach's alpha. From the model above, it can be concluded that it meets the Composite Reliability and Cronbach's Alpha criteria. Hence, the research model meets the Reliability criteria and is a reliable and reliable measuring tool.

4. Conclusion

Based on the research results described in the previous chapter, it can be concluded as follows: 1) Rewards positively and significantly affect the job satisfaction of Grab employees in Jakarta. This means that the higher the reward will increase job satisfaction. 2) Work discipline has a positive and significant effect on the job satisfaction of Grab employees in Jakarta. This means that a higher work discipline will result in more job satisfaction. 3) Rewards do not affect the performance of Grab employees in Jakarta. This means that the lower the reward, the lower the employee's performance. 4) Work discipline has a positive and significant effect on the performance of Grab employees in Jakarta. This means that higher work discipline will result in better employee performance. 5) Job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on the performance of Grab employees in Jakarta. This means that higher job satisfaction will increase employee performance. 6) Job satisfaction mediates the effect of rewards on the performance of Grab employees in Jakarta

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